

COMMERCIAL BANKS ASSETS ARE PROBLEMATIC IN LIGHT OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE AUDIT AND TO TAKE THEM INTO ACCOUNT

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Abstract. Problematic in working with the specific features of the method of commercial bank assets, a conceptual approach to this problem, as well as the lack of assets dedicated to commercial banks and eliminate them avoid problematic in scientific work shows. The economy of the country who justified himself, and mobilizes the capabilities to grow at a high pace all available ettirilayotir continue at the expense of the people of coherent reform strategy is ensured.

Keywords: bank audit, ichi audit, accounting, audit, ifrs.

INTRODUCTION

In particular, in recent years the capitalization of the bank, liquidity and investment activity aimed at further strengthening the resource base and their further improvement of the implementation of consistent and targeted measures as a result of the weight of the assets of the bank is increasing from year to year.

Table 1

Bank of the republic of uzbekistan problematic loans, assets, information on credit and capital¹ (trln. sum)

№	Indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Change (2019/2015)	
							trln. sum	% at
1	Assets ²	57,7	84,1	166,6	214,4	272,7	+215	+372,6
2	risk to subject the assets that	47,0	57,4	106,5	155,0	223,0	+176	+374,5
3	Given loans	39,7	52,6	110,6	167,4	211,6	+171,9	+433,0
4	Capital	7.3 per	9,0	20,7	26,7	51,0	+43,7	+598,6
5	Problematic loans	0,58	0,39	1,32	2,14	3,17	+2,59	+446,6

¹ The official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.cbu.uz) prepared by the author on the basis of data

Assets of the banking system of the republic of uzbekistan for the year 2019 272,7 trln. the sum of the organization, if it has a growth trend compared to last year, than the year 2015 372,6 percent. In the structure of assets are subject to the risk assets, in turn, we will see that the weight is too high of credit, at the same time showing an increase in bank capital to assets that had grown at a higher rate affected. The amount of problematic loans also have a tendency to grow, but less than given credit has increased.

We consider the composition of bank assets in the same place.

Table 2

The composition of commercial bank assets³

Indicator name	2016 y.		2017 y.		2018 y.		Y 2019.		Change, 2019/2016	
	trln. the sum of	the share, in percent	trln. the sum of	the share, in percent	trln. the sum of	the share, in percent	trln. the sum of	the share, in percent	trln. the sum of	share, percent
in cash, cash money and other payment documents	1.3	at 1.6%	4.8	2,9%	to 5.3	2.5%	6,6	2,4%	5,2	0.8% of
Central bank funds	to 12.0	14.2%	14,9	8,9%	11,4	5,3%	14,8	5,4%	2,8	-8,8%
Other banks deposits-resident	4,3	5,1%	6.7	4,0%	6,4	3,0%	10,1	3.7%	5,8	-1,4%
Other banks deposits-residents	6,6	7,8%	18,3	11,0%	13,5	6,3%	15,4	5.7%	8,8	-2,1%
investment dealers and other valuable papers	from 1.5	to 1.8%	at 1.6	1.0	to 2.3	1.1%	3,2	1.2%	1.7	-0,6%
The customer financial instruments on the obligations	of 1.1	increase 1.3% of	2.5	to 1.5%	1,9	0,9%	0.4	0.2%	-0,7	-1,1%
Credit investments, (net)	52,0	61,9%	108,5	65,1%	164,7	76,8%	207,6	76,1%	155,6	14.2%
of the main means, (net)	1.8	2.1%	to 2.3	1.4%	3.5	1.6%	5.7	2.1% of	3,9	0,0%
Assets on accrued interest	0,6	0.7%	1.4	0.8% of	2,8	increase of 1.3%	from 3.3	1.2%	to 2.7	0.5% of
the bank other private property	of 0.4 to	0.5%	0.3	0.2% of	0.2	and 0.1%	0.4	and 0.1%	0,0	-0,4%
Other assets	2,5	2,9%	5,2	manuals 3.1%	2,4	1.1%	to 5.3	1,9%	2,8	-1,0%
Total assets	84,1	100%	166,6	100%	214,4	100%	272,7	100,0%	188,7	0,0%

³ The official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.cbu.uz) prepared by the author on the basis of data

On the basis of the composition of bank assets bank balance sheet is provided in case the data is received. The highest share in the structure of bank assets loans if you have 76,1 percent from the year 2019, total assets, have a tendency to grow compared to last year. This data is taken from the form of the report on the financial condition of commercial banks from netto, that is, the net assets of the bank showed. In the next place credit from the central bank and other deposits in banks takes. Bring credit investment income and other securities dealers who stand in the next place, from the perspective of the share of 1.2 percent in the year 2019, 2016 than 0,6 percent respectively. It is observed that although the main tools of the bank increased the amount of intraoperative assets has share of 2.1 percent. By the bank in the years homo remote banking services, banking services associated with the opening of the center of the main means of acquisition and reconstruction is characterized by an increase in costs.

Basic information on bank assets in the financial statements reflect the structure of the net assets in the bank, which takes as external information on the quality it is good to have for their users. Internal users of accounting assets that deteriorate the quality of accounting are reflected in the accounts of them if you know if you may. Its problematic to suggest that the deterioration of the quality of assets acute.

Commercial banks give credit assets that attract use as the main part of it, not only to generate income, but the funds from the loan should be complete get back to the issue defined in advance. Because the bank as the owner of capital investments, but not certain of the right of use of capital and the interest rate will sell for a certain period on the basis of a must. Also in the country at the same time, the scientific-theoretical and practitioner by scientists problematic credit" as the concept of debate and the debate has been the cause of much more than before. The material of this

course because it is not today the share of loans in the credit portfolio of commercial banks of the republic of problem, including measures to reduce high percent despite much only see it continuing.

Well, what is problematic acute itself, how it appears? If you see looking for the answer to this question.

Literature review of local and foreign scientific and special that we have in them often connects with problematic assets, loans, and "acute problematic", "problematic credit", "credit who do not work", "xarakatsiz credit" with concepts such as represents.

In particular, the credit committee on banking supervision, the federal constitution does not work (aktivní) (np a) loan commitments on bajarilmayotganda, i.e. the customer's bank or credit be available delayed payment more than 90 days of no pay, no pay, ask to see action on (sekryutizasiya, re-financing, restrukturizasiya, payment delay, etc.) you can order is the basis; the payer's ability to pay as a result of a decrease in the presence of your assets qadrsizlanib be; regardless of the number of overdue days, he paid him the full payment of the main debt and interest on the classification provides a possible lack of evidence available at⁴. The federal constitution committee as problematic by its interest payments on term loan and the credit to'lanmasligini noted that more than 90 days.

In international practice is closely related to the concept of problematic credit who do not use credit. Bloem, I am free of the np (non-performing loans) work this basic credit debt and / or interest payments or 90 days or more days with a period of 90 days or more on deposit with pay equal to the delay, kapitallashtirilgan re-

⁴ Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2016) "Guidelines Prudential treatment of problem assets – definitions of non-performing exposures and forbearance", 1-41.

financed loans or deferred by agreement, or payments are 90 days from the duration of many more, at the same time to declare bankruptcy on the debtor of the applicant, similar to the cases there are more serious causes of assets⁵.

Rize province of lenders who do not work (with the np - non-performing loans) of the credit portfolio of the bank it is important to learn because they reflect the quality of the credit portfolio of the banking sector in the country and in general will reflect the quality of stated⁶. Loans that do not work to understand the factors which influence the level of bank risk management of the bank supervisory authorities for the activities of the bank which is responsible for the function and stability is very important.

Rouz peters american bank specialists who conducted research in the field of effective management, in the opinion of the borrower, one or more of the payment or credit decrease the value of supply means that pass into the category of problematic loans⁷. The main focus of the debtor's reason for it professionals will be the focus back guarantee layyoqatsizligi of the loan, the bank overlooked the rest of the risk.

We can see this condition in the near uzbekistan's position, that is, the problematic assets (loans) is "unsatisfactory", "suspicious" and "desperate"⁸ is classified as assets. The central bank of the republic of uzbekistan "on the classification of the quality of assets in commercial banks reserves and assets to

⁵ The Treatment of Nonperforming loans. International Monetary Fund. Prepared by Adriaan M. Bloem and Russel Freeman. Issue Paper Prepared for the July 2005. <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/bop/2005/05-29.pdf>. Issue Paper, 1-15.

⁶ Ozili, P. K. (2019), "Non-Performing Loans and Financial Development: New Evidence", Journal of Risk Finance, February 2019, 1-35.

⁷Роуз П. Банковский менеджмент. Пер. с англ. – М.: Дело, 1997, 192-б.

⁸ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Марказий банкининг "Тижорат банкларида активлар сифатини таснифлаш ва активлар бўйича эҳтимолий йўқотишларни коплаш учун захиралар шакллантириш ҳамда улардан фойдаланиш тартиби тўғрисида" ги 2696-сонли низом. 2015 йил 14 июль

cover losses on the order of probability of their formation and use of a" Cap on the number 2696pay attention to, then as problematic assets over the period, have dropped the rating of the borrower as collateral may decline in value, the customer appears to be operating negative trends in the area, the court focuses attention on the issues of assets to be transferred to the process.

These cases are problematic loans and credit debt foizning description of the deterioration of the timely payment of principal then the customer financial environment, and other circumstances associated with changes in credit terms shows.

H.Otamurodov connects with the reduction of problematic credit credit portfolio management⁹. The main focus in this credit portfolio and credit policy associated with the deterioration of credit quality is seen. The occurrence of more problematic credit the author is tied to the activities of the management of the bank and the customer that may arise in the activities of the rest of the cases negative overlooked.

U.Tuxtabaev coming to be manifest in practice is the result of the credit risk of problematic loans, that is, not the proper management of the credit risk of the effects will be¹⁰. The payment of the loan and its interest in the credit risk of the occurrence of the soup in and out of their time onirilmasligini produces, that is, the emergence of problems in the activity of the client, the timely payment of the loan and its interest to give vomiting.

⁹ Otamurodov, H.H. (2018) "Current basis of management of the bank credit portfolio in Uzbekistan" International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, Vol. VI, Issue 12, 169-179.

¹⁰ Тухтабаев У.А. Муаммоли кредитлар ва уларни баргараф этиш йўллари. и.ф.н. илмий даражасини олиш учун дисс. Автореферати. – Т.: 2008. – 24 б.

Either. Abdullaev, T. Qoraliev keltirmayotgan the term of the loan benefits past loans and other problematic¹¹ as it does not look. Over the period of the return of the authors credit, they recognized the timely payment of interest on credit arising spark not problematic, but how the credit was to be problematic term, the reasons for its occurrence are not clear.

Sh. Accurate information on the quality of the bank's credit portfolio and its abdullayeva have not the necessary measures in cases of pre-risks that may arise as a result of problematic loans and is set to deliver the minimum level of¹² will note. The author's problematic indicates that a decrease in the quality of credit portfolio credit is available, then the effective management of the loan portfolio will have to go get to work on that pointed.

H. Rahmatov the formation of stable assets in the practice of banks of the economic system that lead to a decrease problematic, tijorat banks to protect their assets in such conditions, reduce the risk of problematic loans and deferment of payments necessary to create an early warning system to eliminate the effects of effective they¹³ noted that it was stained. Thus, the record will also show the point of impact makrodarajada their assets appear to be problematic.

L. Dudines the return of their assets or from work or who poses placing them problematic banks cannot doubt the possibility of the bank's assets have economic benefits¹⁴ as it does not look. Bank assets taken into account in this recipe as given in the definition of the types of assets you can look without problematic.

¹¹ Абдуллаев Ё., Қоралиев Т., Тошмуродов Ш., Абдуллаева С. Банк иши. Ўқув қўлланма-Т.: “IQTISOD-MOLIYA”, 2009 йил, 548 бет.

¹² Ш.З.Абдуллаева. Банк рисклари ва кредитлаш. –Т.: Молия, 2002. 304 б.

¹³ Раҳматов Х.Ў. “Иқтисодий диверсификациялаш шароитида тижорат банк активлари самарадорлигини ошириш масалари” DSc илмий даражаси олиш учун ёзган диссертация автореферати. –Т.: 2020, 66 бет.

¹⁴ Дудинец Л.А. Теоретические подходы к определению сущности проблемных активов банка. Экономика и банки, (2), 28-35. <http://ojs.polessu.by/EB/article/view/398>

In the opinion of the bank mwill be eligible to enter the aim of assets uammoli the following approach: acute problematic - placed the resources of the bank or the bank may return a portion of this is not going to be out of the disposal of, not losses that may arise as a result of income (loss) for the risk of the bank's assets and financial liabilities.

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